

Antibody Characterization Report for NLRP3 (UniProt ID: Q96P20)

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

Author(s): Riham Ayoubi¹, Sara González Bolívar¹, Peter S. McPherson¹ and Carl Laflamme^{1*}

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Target:

Protein name used in this report: NLRP3

Recommended protein name: NACHT, LRR and PYD domains-containing protein 3

Gene name: *NLRP3*

Uniprot: Q96P20

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized fourteen NLRP3 commercial antibodies for western blot and immunoprecipitation [2, 3] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. A THP-1 *NLRP3* KO line is available at Abcam and was used in this study. THP-1 was selected based on evidence of appropriate NLRP3 protein expression determined through [4, 5].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab281894	CVCL_0006	THP-1	WT
Abcam	ab280063	CVCL_B9Z7	THP-1	<i>NLRP3</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the NLRP3 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab263899**	1007080-36	AB_2889890	recombinant-mono	EPR23094-1	rabbit	0.58	Wb, IP
Abclonal	A21906	5500037920	AB_3083447	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2.40	Wb, IF
Bio-Techne	MAB7578*	CGSM0323032	AB_2889405	monoclonal	768319	rat	0.50	Wb, IF
Bio-Techne	NBP2-03948*	D150755	AB_3076153	monoclonal	25N10E9	mouse	1.00	Wb
Bio-Techne	NBP2-12446	D116879-1	AB_2750946	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IP, IF
Cell Signaling Technology	13158**	5	AB_2798134	recombinant-mono	D2P5E	rabbit	0.45	Wb, IP
Cell Signaling Technology	15101**	6	AB_2722591	recombinant-mono	D4D8T	rabbit	0.36	Wb, IP
GeneTex	GTX106313	44454	AB_1951002	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.70	Wb
GeneTex	GTX133569	43838	AB_2887025	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.57	Wb
GeneTex	GTX639954**	T-45348	AB_3096028	recombinant-mono	HL2813	rabbit	0.24	Wb
Proteintech	27458-1-AP	0118512	AB_2923578	polyclonal		rabbit	0.80	Wb, IP, IF
Proteintech	68102-1-Ig*	10037603	AB_2923634	monoclonal	3H1A7	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-32255**	YK4132043	AB_2809541	recombinant-mono	SC06-23	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-34969*	YJ4089072A	AB_2809339	monoclonal	CL0210	mouse	1.00	Wb, IF

Wb=western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All the NLRP3 antibodies tested are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit, anti-mouse, and anti-rat antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120, 62-6520, and 31470, respectively). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit, anti-mouse and anti-rat secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A-21429, A-21424 and A-21434, respectively).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 (ATCC modification) (Gibco, cat. number A1049101) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 0.05 mM 2-Mercaptoethanol (Gibco, cat. number 21985023, 2 mM L-glutamine (Wisent cat. number 609-065), 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

THP-1 WT and *NLRP3* KO (listed in Table 1) were treated with 200 ng/ml of phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) (Abcam, cat. number ab147465) for 2 days. 200 ng/ml of PMA was added to fresh medium in both day 1 and day 2 [6].

To collect culture medium for western blot, cells were starved in RPMI 1640, 0.05 mM 2-Mercaptoethanol, 2 mM L-glutamine and 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin.

Antibody screening by western blot on lysate

Western blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [3]. THP-1 WT and *NLRP3* KO (listed in Table 1) treated or not with PMA were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher

Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by western blot on culture medium

THP-1 WT and *NLRP3* KO cells were washed 3x with PBS 1x and starved for ~18 hrs. Culture media were collected and centrifuged for 10 min at 500 x g to eliminate cells and larger contaminants, then for 10 min at 4500 x g to eliminate smaller contaminants. Culture media were concentrated by centrifuging at 4000 x g for 30min using Amicon Ultra-15 Centrifugal Filter Units with a membrane NMWL of 10kDa (MilliporeSigma cat. number UFC901024). Culture media were supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on lysate

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [3]. Antibody-beads conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse and rat antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

PMA-treated THP-1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine

polyacrylamide gels. Prot-A:HRP (Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291) was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 1.0 µg/ml.

Figure 1: NLRP3 antibody screening by western blot on lysate

Figure 2: NLRP3 antibody screening by western blot on culture medium

Figure 3: NLRP3 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on lysate

Figure 1: NLRP3 antibody screening by western blot on lysate.

Lysates of THP-1 WT and *NLRP3* KO were prepared, and 20 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated NLRP3 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab263899** at 1/1000, A21906 at 1/3000, MAB7578* at 1/200, NBP2-03948* at 1/250, NBP2-12446 at 1/250, 13158** at 1/500, 15101** at 1/500, GTX106313 at 1/500, GTX133569 at 1/500, GTX639954** at 1/500, 27458-1-AP at 1/1000, 68102-1-Ig* at 1/500, MA5-32255** at 1/100, MA5-34969* at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 118 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: NLRP3 antibody screening by western blot on culture medium.

THP-1 WT and *NLRP3* KO were cultured in serum-free medium, and 20 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated NLRP3 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: ab263899** at 1/1000, A21906 at 1/3000, MAB7578* at 1/200, NBP2-03948* at 1/250, NBP2-12446 at 1/250, 13158** at 1/500, 15101** at 1/500, GTX106313 at 1/500, GTX133569 at 1/500, GTX639954** at 1/500, 27458-1-AP at 1/1000, 68102-1-Ig* at 1/500, MA5-32255** at 1/100, MA5-34969* at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 118 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 3: NLRP3 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation on lysate.

THP-1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated NLRP3 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated NLRP3 antibody. For western blot, 13158** was used at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate; n/s=nonspecific signal. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

References

1. Laflamme, C., et al., *Opinion: Independent third-party entities as a model for validation of commercial antibodies*. N Biotechnol, 2021. **65**: p. 1-8 DOI: 10.1016/j.nbt.2021.07.001.
2. Laflamme, C., et al., *Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72*. Elife, 2019. **8** DOI: 10.7554/eLife.48363.
3. Ayoubi, R., et al., *A consensus platform for antibody characterization*. 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1>.
4. Nusinow, D.P., et al., *Quantitative Proteomics of the Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia*. Cell, 2020. **180**(2): p. 387-402 e16 DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2019.12.023.
5. *DepMap, Broad*. 2019.
6. Starr, T., et al., *The phorbol 12-myristate-13-acetate differentiation protocol is critical to the interaction of THP-1 macrophages with Salmonella Typhimurium*. PLoS One, 2018. **13**(3): p. e0193601 DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0193601.